

Kinetics of Alkaline Chloramine-T Oxidation of Glutamic Acid with and without Catalytic Action of Cu(II) Ion

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A kinetic study of the oxidation of glutamic acid by chloramine-T in aqueous alkaline media has been made. The findings follow the expression :

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{CAT}] = \frac{[\text{CAT}][\text{S}^-]}{[\text{NaOH}]}, \text{ when } [\text{NaOH}] < 4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$$

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{CAT}] = [\text{CAT}][\text{S}^-], \text{ when } [\text{NaOH}] > 4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$$

Similarly, for Cu(II) catalysed reaction

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{CAT}] = \frac{[\text{CAT}][\text{S}^-][\text{Cu(II)}]}{[\text{NaOH}]}, \text{ when } [\text{NaOH}] < 4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$$

which assumes the form

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{CAT}] = [\text{CAT}][\text{S}^-][\text{Cu(II)}], \text{ when } [\text{NaOH}] > 4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$$

Cu(II) catalyses the reaction and the catalytic action of Cu(II) is ascribed to the complex formation with glutamic acid anion. A negligible influence of added neutral salt on the reaction rate indicates interaction between a neutral molecule and an ion in the rate-determining step.

THE kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of amino acids by chloramine-T have been reported¹⁻³.

Despite the biological significance of the catalytic function of Cu(II) and its formation of complex during amino acid metabolism⁴, the kinetic study on Cu(II) catalysed alkaline chloramine-T oxidation of amino acids has not been emphasised to the satisfaction. However, a very few reports⁵⁻⁷ pertaining to such studies have been brought out recently. These findings prompted us to investigate oxidation mechanism of glutamic acid by alkaline chloramine-T, in the absence of Cu(II) and in its presence as a catalyst.

Experimental

Aqueous chloramine-T solution was prepared from an E. Merck, G. R. sample and the concentration was checked iodometrically. Aqueous glutamic acid solution was prepared from B. D. H., A. R. reagent and its strength was checked by Sorensen formol titration method. All other reagents were of analytical grade and their solutions were prepared by dissolving the appropriate quantities in double distilled water. The reaction vessels were coated black from outside by Japan black to exclude photochemical effects⁸.

The kinetics of the reactions was followed by estimating the change in chloramine-T content with time. 5 ml. of the reaction mixture were withdrawn

at definite intervals and the unconsumed chloramine-T was estimated iodometrically⁹.

Results and Discussion

Effect of chloramine-T :

The order of reaction in chloramine-T, both in absence and in presence of Cu(II), was determined by carrying out the reaction at different initial concentrations of the oxidant. It followed a pseudo first order dependence at all the concentrations of chloramine-T. The first order rate constants are displayed in Table 1.

TABLE 1

		[Glutamic Acid] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, [NaOH] = 4.0×10^{-3} M, Temp. = 36°								
		[Chloramine-T] $\times 10^{-3}$ M								
		0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	
$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		2.92	3.18	3.10	2.18	2.83	3.09	2.81	3.14	
$k_1' \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		4.10	4.00	4.01	3.85	3.96	3.94	4.02	3.92	
k_1' is the first order rate constant in presence of 1.0×10^{-3} M copper sulphate.										

Effect of glutamic acid :

To ascertain reaction rate dependence and the order of reaction in substrate concentration, the

reactions were carried out at different concentrations of glutamic acid, both in absence and presence of Cu(II). Table 2 records the results obtained by such studies.

TABLE 2

[Chloramine-T] = 1.0×10^{-3} M ; [NaOH] = 4.0×10^{-2} M ;
Temp. = 36°

[Glutamic Acid] $\times 10^3$ M	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	k_1 [Glutamic Acid]	$k'_1 \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	k'_1 [Glutamic Acid]
0.8	2.52	3.15	3.40	4.25
0.9	2.84	3.15	3.79	4.21
1.1	3.33	3.03	4.32	3.92
1.2	3.65	3.04	4.93	4.11
1.3	3.88	2.98	5.54	4.26
1.4	4.26	3.04	5.99	4.28

k'_1 is first order rate constant in the presence of 0.4×10^{-3} M copper sulphate.

The first order rate constants are found to be proportional to the substrate concentration in both uncatalysed and Cu(II) catalysed reactions. The overall bimolecular rate constants k_1 /[glutamic acid] and k'_1 /[glutamic acid] show constant values confirming first order dependence in substrate concentrations both in absence and in presence of Cu(II).

Effect of NaOH :

Dependence on sodium hydroxide has been studied by keeping the concentrations of oxidant and substrate fixed and varying the concentration of NaOH. Observations are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3

[Chloramine-T] = 1.0×10^{-3} M ; [Glutamic acid] = 1.0×10^{-3} M ;
Temp. = 36°

	[NaOH] $\times 10^2$ M							
	2.8	3.2	3.6	4.0	4.4	4.8	5.6	6.0
$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	4.46	4.03	3.54	3.10	2.61	2.08	2.08	1.91
$k_1 \times [\text{NaOH}] \times 10^4 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.25	1.29	1.27	1.24	1.15	-	-	-

The product of [NaOH] and the first order rate constant is constant when $[\text{NaOH}] < 4.8 \times 10^{-2}$ M, which suggests inverse first order when [NaOH] is less than 4.8×10^{-2} M. The constancy of the rate constant values beyond 4.4×10^{-2} M NaOH shows independence of reaction rate at high alkali concentration.

Similar effects of [NaOH] on the Cu(II) catalysed oxidation reaction have been observed.

Effect of CuSO_4 :

The first order rate constants observed at a perceptible range of Cu(II) concentration ($0.1-0.6 \times 10^{-3}$ M) were plotted against copper sulphate concentration (Fig. 1). With Cu(II) concentrations $< 0.4 \times 10^{-3}$ M, the observed rate constant increased linearly with increase in Cu(II) concentration. However, at Cu(II) concentrations higher than 0.4×10^{-3} M, no further increase in rate constant values was observed. The extrapolation of the curve to zero Cu(II) concentration gives an intercept on rate constant axis, which corresponds to the value of uncatalysed oxidation. This clearly indicates that the observed rate constant comprised two terms and can be expressed as :

$$k'_1 = k_{\text{uncat}} + k_{\text{cat}}$$

Obviously the rate of chloramine-T disappearance is given by

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] = \frac{k_{\text{uncat}}[\text{CAT}][\text{substrate}]}{[\text{NaOH}]} + \frac{k_{\text{cat}}[\text{CAT}][\text{S}][\text{Cu(II)}]}{[\text{NaOH}]}$$

Effect of salts :

Both uncatalysed and Cu(II) catalysed reactions were studied in presence of neutral salts, KNO_3 , NaNO_3 , K_2SO_4 and $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, each in the concentration range of $1.0-3.0 \times 10^{-3}$ M. The specific reaction rate was found to be completely independent of the added ionic strength to the reaction mixture.

Fig. 1

Effect of temperature :

Table 4 gives the rate constant values at different temperatures both for uncatalysed and Cu(II) catalysed reactions. Plots of $\log k_1$ and k'_1 vs $1/T$ were straight lines. The energies of activation were calculated from the slope of these plots and found to be 15.6 kcal/mole and 15.0 kcal/mole for uncatalysed and Cu(II) catalysed reactions, respectively.

TABLE 4

[Chloramine-T] = 1.0×10^{-3} M ; [Glutamic acid] = 1.0×10^{-3} M ;
[NaOH] = 4.0×10^{-3} M

	Temp. °C				
$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	32.5	36.5	41.0	45.0	47.5
$k'_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	2.32	3.10	4.72	6.69	7.81
	3.11	4.01	6.30	8.47	9.63

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

In order to substantiate and proposed mechanism, the stoichiometry of the reaction was determined. The reaction mixtures containing varying ratios of chloramine-T to glutamic acid were equilibrated for 75 hr at room temp. and the unconsumed chloramine-T was estimated at the end of the period. The findings indicated that one mole of glutamic acid consumed two moles of chloramine-T. Product analysis^{1,2} indicated the formation of nitrile.

Uncatalysed oxidation of glutamic acid followed a first order dependence each in chloramine-T and reducing substrate. A negative single order dependence was reported in alkali. A negligible salt effect corroborates the interaction between neutral molecule and an ion.

A mechanism is proposed in which the initial step is the hydrolysis of chloramine-T.

The essential reaction sequences involved are

Thus the rate of disappearance of chloramine-T is

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] = k_2[\text{CAT}][\text{glutamic acid}] + k_3[\text{X}][\text{CAT}] \quad \dots (A)$$

By applying steady state treatment and approximation that water is in large excess and $k_{-1}[\text{NaOH}] > 2k_2[\text{S}^-]$, the rate law is obtained as :

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_{-1}} \frac{[\text{CAT}][\text{S}^-]}{[\text{NaOH}]}, \quad \text{when } [\text{NaOH}] < 4.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M} \quad \dots (B)$$

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] = k_6[\text{CAT}][\text{S}^-], \quad \text{when } [\text{NaOH}] > 4.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M} \quad \dots (C)$$

The glutamic acid anion reacts with Cu(II) ion reversibly and slowly generating CuGA.

Along with the steps (2) and (3) the following steps also occur simultaneously

On applying steady state treatment to the steps (1), (2), (3), (5) and (6), the following rate expression is obtained

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_{-1}} \frac{[\text{CAT}][\text{GA}^-]}{[\text{NaOH}]} + \frac{2k_1k_5}{k_{-1}} \frac{[\text{CAT}][\text{CuGA}]}{[\text{NaOH}]} \quad \dots (D)$$

From equation (4)

$$[\text{CuGA}] = \frac{k_4}{k_{-4}} [\text{Cu(II)}][\text{GA}^-]$$

This value is fed into expression (D) to get

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] = \frac{2k_1}{k_{-1}} \frac{[\text{CAT}][\text{GA}^-]}{[\text{NaOH}]} \left\{ k_2 + \frac{k_4k_5}{k_{-4}} [\text{Cu(II)}] \right\} \quad \dots (E)$$

This shows linear dependence of reaction rate on Cu(II) concentration.

At high Cu(II) concentration i.e. $[\text{Cu(II)}] > 0.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, the whole of the substrate is oxidised by reaction sequences (5) and (6) and thus the steps (2) and (3) are completely skipped. The rate of reaction can be given as :

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_{-1}} \frac{[\text{CAT}][\text{CuGA}]}{[\text{NaOH}]} \quad \dots (F)$$

Here $[\text{CuGA}] = [\text{GA}]$ and thus an optimum value of rate constant is inevitable at high Cu(II) concentration.

At high alkali concentration, when $[\text{NaOH}] > 4.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, the rate of Cu(II) catalysed reaction becomes independent of alkali concentration. Therefore, the rate expression assumes the form

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] = k'_6 [\text{CAT}][\text{S}^-] [\text{Cu(II)}] \quad \dots (G)$$

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